

ANALYSIS OF SCIENCE STUDENTS' SSCE RESULT USING PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This research work intends to detect the subjects that contribute to the inconsistency in the relationship among the subjects of studied by using the method of Principal Component Analysis that was used to investigate the variability among the subjects. The data used for the analysis is students' WAEC results for the year 2011, Federal Science College, Sokoto. Out of fourteen subjects areas which the students sat for, nine subjects were used for the study. Single sets were formed that consists Economics, Geography, English Language, Hausa-Language, Mathematics, Agricultural Science, Biology, Chemistry, and Physics. Nine Components were formed, while only six Components were considered showing the subjects that contribute significantly to the variation and inconsistency among the subjects. However, there should be concentration on the subjects that contribute a high variation to check the students' performance.

INTRODUCTION

Principal component analysis is one of the methods that can be used to analyse multivariate dataset. It can reduce the dimensionality of large data set which consists of a number of interrelated variables to smaller components (Hussain et. al. 2011).

Several authors including Anderson (1958), Marada, et. al.(1979), Jolliffe (1986), Hair et. al. (1998), Anderson, et. al. (1998) established that in principal component Analysis, we seek to maximize the variance of a linear combination of the variables. Essentially, Principal component is a one-sample technique applied to data with no groupings among the observations and no partitioning of the variables into subset y and x. Principal components are concerned only with the core structure of a single sample of observations on p variables. None of the variables is designated as dependent, and no grouping of observations is assumed (Rencher, 2002). The first principal component is the linear combination with maximal variance; we are essentially searching for a dimension along which the observations are maximally separated or spread out. The second principal component is the linear combination with maximal variance in a direction orthogonal to the first principal component, and so on.

Principal components are used to reduce the number of dimensions. Another useful dimension reduction device is to evaluate the first two principal components for each observation vector and construct a scatter plot to check for multivariate normality, outliers, and so on. Everitt and Dunn (1991) and Antonio, et. al.(2010) pointed out that, in general, the first few principal components are sensitive to outliers that inflate variances or distort co variances, and the last few are sensitive to outliers that introduce artificial dimensions or mask singularities.

For example, we might want to rank students on the basis of their scores on achievement test in English, Mathematics, Reading, and so on. An average score would provide a single scale on which to compare the students, but with unequal weights we can spread the students out further on the scale and obtain a better ranking.

Data used for the Analysis

The data used for the study were collected from Federal Science College, Sokoto.

The data consist of scores of 100 students for 2011 WEST AFRICA EXAMINATION COUNCIL (WAEC) Exams. Out of Fourteen Subjects areas which the students sat for, nine subjects are used. The selection was based on the number of students that sat for the interested subjects of study. The nine subjects were put in a

single Set. The Set consists of Economics, Geography, English Language, Hausa-Language, Mathematics, Agricultural Science, Biology, Chemistry, and Physics.

Principal Component Analysis

The steps involved in the analysis of principal component analysis include the following methods as below. Algebraically, principal components are particular linear combinations of the p random variables.

Geometrically, these linear combinations represent the selection of new coordinate system obtained by rotating the original system with their development and does not require a multivariate normal assumption. On the other hand, principal components derived for multivariate normal populations have useful interpretations in terms of the constant ellipsoids.

Step 1: get the data

Consider the linear combinations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Y_1 &= a_1'X = a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + \dots + a_{1p}X_p \\
 Y_2 &= a_2'X = a_{21}X_1 + a_{22}X_2 + \dots + a_{2p}X_p \\
 &\cdot \\
 &\cdot \\
 &\cdot \\
 Y_p &= a_p'X = a_{p1}X_1 + a_{p2}X_2 + \dots + a_{pp}X_p
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.1}$$

Step 2: standardise the data

Sometimes it makes sense to compute principal component for raw data. This is appropriate when all the variables are in the same units. Standardizing the data is often preferable when the variables are in different units or when the variance of different columns is substantial. This can be done by subtracting the means of each column and dividing by its standard deviation namely:

$$Z = \frac{(X - \mu_i)}{\sqrt{\sigma_{ii}}} , \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, p \tag{3.2}$$

In matrix notation, it is given by:

$$Z = (V^{1/2})^{-1}(X - \mu) \tag{3.3}$$

where $V^{1/2}$ is the diagonal standard deviation matrix. From this, we obtain mean of Z equal zero, $E(Z) = 0$.

Step 3: calculate the covariance matrix.

Further, the covariance matrix of Z is calculated using the formula below

$$COV(Z) = (V^{1/2})^{-1} \Sigma (V^{1/2})^{-1} = \rho \tag{3.4}$$

where ρ also known as correlation.

Step 4: calculate the eigenvectors and Eigen values of the covariance matrix

The principal components of Z may be obtained from eigenvectors of the correlation matrix ρ of X, refer to equation (1.3).

